

PLANNING ANALISYS OF THE EXPANSION LTE AND LTE-A NETWORK IN GARUT DISTRICT

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Abstract

Garut district is a tourist destination visited by tourists in West Java. In this area there are some excellent tourist attractions such as Cikembulan Animal Park, Puncak Darajat and Cipanas, that every day in the coming thousands of tourists. The need for voice and data communications services is needed in this area. The condition of the LTE network in Garut district area is not fully uniform. Based on survey results, blank spot problems (RSRP > -100 dBm), poor signal quality (SINR > -20 dB), and low throughput in some sub-districts were founded. To overcome this problems, LTE network expansion planning needs to be done in some sub-districts. Expansion planning is carried out using two scenarios, LTE (FDD) at 1800 MHz and LTE-A using carrier aggregation methods at 850 MHz and 1800 MHz combined with SFR.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2541284

I. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the 4G LTE network is not yet fully distributed to every region. Currently only major cities that have been covered this service such as Jakarta, Bandung, Bogor, Tasikmalaya, Sukabumi, etc.. In fact, there are still potential market locations that need more service 4G network is one of them is the district of Garut. Garut regency is a busy tourist destination visited by tourists in West Java. LTE network conditions in the district of Garut is currently only located in the city center with a small coverage and performance that has not been optimal. Based on the survey results, blank spot problems (RSRP > -100dBm), poor signal quality (SINR > -20 dB), and slow data throughput.

II. BASIC THEORY

A. Capacity Planning

Capacity-based planning is carried out for planning that prioritizes the fulfillment of user traffic requirements. Data estimated number of subscribers in some districts in Garut region obtained from the Central Statistics Agency for Garut district area. There is an equation used to perform expansion planning based on capacity ie:

$$T/S = ST \times SDR \times BR \times [1/(1-BLER)] \quad (1)$$

$$SUT = [(\sum (T/S) \times BHSA \times Px (1+PAPR)]/3600 \quad (2)$$

$$NT (IP) = SUT \times \text{Total Target User} \quad (3)$$

$$NT (MAC) = UL NT / 0.98 \quad (4)$$

$$DLCC+CRC=(168-36-12) \times CB \times CR \times N \times C \times 1000 \quad (5)$$

This research is in part supported by the Telkom University Scientific Research Grant.

$$ULCC+CRC=(168-24) \times CB \times CR \times N \times C \times 1000 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Capacity/site} = 3 \times \text{Cell Average Throughput} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Number site} = NT / (\text{Capacity/site}) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Cell for 3 Sector} = \sqrt{\text{Cell Coverage} / (2.6 \times 1.95)} \quad (9)$$

Where :

- T/S = Throughput/ Session (kbit)
SDR = Session Duty Ratio
BR = Bearer Rate (kbps)
DLCC = Downlink Cell Capacity (kbps)
ULCC = Uplink Cell Capacity (kbps)
SUT = Single User Throughput (kbps)
N = Number of Resource Block
C = Transmitter
PAPR = Peak Average Power Ratio (%)
NT(IP) = Network Throughput (kbps)
NT(MAC)= Network Throughput MAC Layer (kbps)

B. Coverage planning

Coverage planning is a cellular network planning method to ensure the network can provide services/ signals throughout the review area. There are several equations that are used to perform expansion plans based on coverage:

$$\text{MAPL} = (\text{EIRP}/\text{Sc}) - \text{MSR} - \text{PL} - \text{SFM} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{EIRP}/\text{Sc} = \text{PSc} + \text{Tx AG} - \text{Tx CL} - \text{BL} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Psc} = \text{PTx} - 10 \text{ Log} (\text{NSc}) \quad (12)$$

$$\text{MSR} = \text{SRx} - \text{Rx AG} + \text{Rx CL} + \text{Rx BL} + \text{M} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{SRx} = (\text{TN}/\text{Sc}) + \text{NF} \text{ eNodeB} + \text{SINR} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{TN}/\text{Sc} = 10 \text{ Log} (\text{K} \times \text{T} \times \text{W}) \quad (15)$$

$$\text{Wide of Cell} = 1.95 \times \text{d}^2 \quad (16)$$

$$\sum \text{LTE} = \text{Total wide area} / \text{wide of cell} \quad (17)$$

Where :

- MAPL = Maximum Allowable Pathloss (dB)
EIRP = Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (dBm)
Sc = Subcarrier
MSR = Minimum Signal Strength (dBm)
PL = Penetration Loss (dB)
AG = Antenna Gain (dBi)
CL = Cable Loss (dB)
BL = Body Loss (dB)
TN = Thermal Noise (dB)
NF = Noise Figure (dB)
K = Boltzman Constant
T = Temperature (K)
W = Bandwidth (Hz)

C. Propagation Model

The propagation model is used to calculate the cell radius (d). The propagation model used in this research is Cost-231 and Okumura Hatta.

Okumura Hatta equation :

$$\text{Lu} = 69.55 + 26.16 \log f - 13.82 \log h_b - \text{Ch} + [44.9 - 6.55 \log b] \log d \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Ch} = (1.1 \log f - 0.7) \text{hr} - (1.56 \log f - 0.8) \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Cost -231 equation : Ch} = (1.1 \log f - 0.7) \text{hr} - (1.56 \text{ Log F} - 0.8) \quad (20)$$

$$\text{PL} = 46.3 + 33.9(\log f) - 13.82 \log h_b - \text{Ch} + (44.9 - 6.55 \log b) \log d + c \quad (21)$$

D. Soft Frequency Reuse (SFR)

Soft Frequency Reuse is a reuse frequency scheme where the coverage area is divided into two areas: cell center and cell edge. Cell center is a coverage area with cell radius using subband bandwidth by

using transmit power. Cell edge is a cell coverage area with a cell radius using a reuse frequency scheme greater than one and using cell center transmit power.

[7][8]

E. Key Performance Indicator (KPI)

Key Performance Indicator (KPI) contains parameters that are indicators to determine the performance of a network. Each of these parameters has a target KPI that must be achieved to meet the quality of the network.

TABLE 1 KPI TARGET FOR EACH PARAMETER

Objective	Parameter	Target KPI
Accessibility	User Connected	$\geq 90\%$
Coverage	RSRP	$90\% \geq -100\text{dBm}$
Signal Quality	SINR	$90\% \geq 5 \text{ dB}$
ServiceIntegrity	Throughput	$\geq 12 \text{ Mbps}$

III. THE EXPANSION PLANNING NETWORK

A. Flowchart

Figure.1. Flowchart for expansion planning stage

B. Measurement Initial Condition

With SINR values ranging from 0 to -20 dB. This proves that in the sub-district there is no LTE (blank spot) network.

C. Expansion Planning Scenarios

In this study, the LTE network expansion plan using two scenarios of LTE (FDD) and LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) combined with SFR. In the planning scenario of expansion of coverage area with LTE (FDD) used frequency 1800 MHz, while in planning expansion of coverage area of LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) use frequency 1800-850 MHz with total bandwidth 15 MHz.

D. Expansion Planning Based on Capacity

(1) Forecasting of Number User

- Population number 2022 = 551,565 user
- Productive Age 65% = 357,106 user
- Market share operator 40% = 142,842 user
- Penetration of LTE 25% = 35,711 user
- Penetration of LTE-A 25% = 16,070 user

(2) Service Model and Traffic Model

Service model is a reference minimum number of throughput so customers can access the service. Service model is used to know the value of throughput / session. Traffic model is a model of traffic used as a reference to calculate the single user throughput for each service.

TABLE 2 SERVICE MODEL AND TRAFFIC MODEL

Trafik Parameter	Uplink	Downlink	Sub Urban	
	Throughput/Session (kbps)	Throughput/Session (kbps)	Traffic Penetration	BHSA
VoIP	869.49	869.49	100%	1.9
Video Phone	4421.31	4421.31	35%	0.45
Video Convergence	113690.91	113690.91	17%	0.33
Real Time Gaming	11367.27	90952.73	40%	1.37
Streaming Media	5683.64	864016.36	20%	3.05
IMS Signalling	22.10	22.10	40%	4
Web Browsing	5684.55	22737.27	100%	3.5
File Transfer	85272.73	454751.52	30%	0.2
Email	7106.06	37895.96	55%	0.45
P2P File Sharing	303151.52	909503.03	26%	0.4

(3) Single User Throughput

Single user throughput is the minimum amount of throughput every customer must have to access all services.

TABLE 3 SINGLE USER THROUGHPUT

Trafik	VoIP	Video Phone	Video Conference	Real Time Gaming	Streaming Media	Web Browsing	File Transfer	Email	P2P File Sharing	Total	Single User Throughput (Kbps)
UL	1817.24	765.99	7015.87	6852.19	3813.72	21885.50	5628.00	1934.63	34680.53	84432.57	23.4535
DL	9240.54	765.99	7015.87	54826.30	579754.98	87538.50	30013.60	10317.18	104047.15	883559.01	245.4331

(4) Network Throughput

Network throughput is the amount of throughput required for the entire number of users planned in accessing all services. Network throughput was obtained by multiplying a single user throughput value with 35,711 users for LTE (FDD) networks and 16,070 users for LTE-A (carrier aggregation) networks.

TABLE 4 NETWORK THROUGHPUT

Parameter	LTE (FDD)		LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation)	
	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink	Downlink
Total Target User	35711		16070	
Single User Throughput (Kbps)	23.4535	245.4331	23.4535	245.4331
Network Throughput (IP) (Kbps)	837547.6866	8764659.946	376898.6317	3944109.247
Network Throughput (IP) (Mbps)	837.55	8764.66	3768.99	3944.11

Figure 2. Drivetest Result for RSRP & SINR

The existing area of LTE network is located in Garut subdistrict. The value of RSRP in some districts other than Garut Kota is located in the range of -102 dBm to -150 dBm

(5) Radio Overhead

Radio Overhead serves to convert throughput across IP layer to MAC layer, after the addition of header of 0.98 in each layer drop.

TABLE 5 MAC LAYER THROUGHPUT

LTE (FDD)		LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation)	
DL Network Throughput (Mbps)	UL Network Throughput (Mbps)	DL Network Throughput (Mbps)	UL Network Throughput (Mbps)
8939.8816	854.2918	4022.9592	384.4325

(6) Average Distribution of SINR

The SINR distribution table is used to calculate cell capacity and site capacity from both uplink and downlink sides.

TABLE 6 AVERAGE DISTRIBUTION OF SINR

Modulation	Code Bit	Code Rate	SINR (min) (dB)	SINR Proba Inity (Pa)	DL Cell Throughput (Mbps) (Ra)	DL Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)	UL Cell Throughput (Mbps) (Ra)	UL Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)	Modulation	Code Bit	Code Rate	SINR (min) (dB)	SINR Proba Inity (Pa)	DL Cell Throughput (Mbps) (Ra)	DL Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)	UL Cell Throughput (Mbps) (Ra)	UL Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)
QPSK 1/3	2	0.3	-1.5 - 0.3	0.29	7.199976	2.0880	8.639976	2.5056	QPSK 1/3	2	0.3	-1.5 - 0.3	0.29	7.199976	2.0880	8.639976	2.5056
QPSK 1/2	2	0.5	0.3 - 2	0.27	11.999976	3.2400	14.399976	3.8880	QPSK 1/2	2	0.5	0.3 - 2	0.27	11.999976	3.2400	14.399976	3.8880
QPSK 2/3	2	0.67	2 - 4.5	0.19	16.079976	3.0552	19.299976	3.6662	QPSK 2/3	2	0.67	2 - 4.5	0.19	16.079976	3.0552	19.299976	3.6662
16 QAM 1/4	4	0.5	4.5 - 6	0.15	23.999976	3.6000	28.799976	4.3200	16 QAM 1/4	4	0.5	4.5 - 6	0.15	23.999976	3.6000	28.799976	4.3200
16 QAM 2/3	4	0.67	6 - 8.5	0.14	32.159976	4.5024	38.591976	5.4029	16 QAM 2/3	4	0.67	6 - 8.5	0.14	32.159976	4.5024	38.591976	5.4029
16 QAM 4/5	4	0.8	8.5 - 10.8	0.09	38.399976	3.4560	46.079976	4.1472	16 QAM 4/5	4	0.8	8.5 - 10.8	0.09	38.399976	3.4560	46.079976	4.1472
64 QAM 1/4	6	0.5	10.8 - 12.5	0.06	35.999976	2.1600	43.199976	2.5920	64 QAM 1/4	6	0.5	10.8 - 12.5	0.06	35.999976	2.1600	43.199976	2.5920
64 QAM 2/3	6	0.67	12.5 - 13.5	0.05	48.239976	2.4120	57.887976	2.8944	64 QAM 2/3	6	0.67	12.5 - 13.5	0.05	48.239976	2.4120	57.887976	2.8944
Cell Average Throughput (MAC) = $\sum Pa \times Ra$								24.5136	Cell Average Throughput (MAC) = $\sum Pa \times Ra$								24.5136
Capacity per site								73.5407	Capacity per site								73.5407

(a) 1800 MHz

(b) 850 MHz

Modulation	Code Bit	Code Rate	SINR (min) (dB)	SINR Proba Inity (Pa)	DL Cell Throughput (Mbps) (Ra)	DL Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)	UL Cell Throughput (Mbps) (Ra)	UL Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)
QPSK 1/3	2	0.3	-1.5 - 0.3	0.31	21.599976	6.6960	12.939976	4.0176
QPSK 1/2	2	0.5	0.3 - 2	0.39	35.999976	14.0400	21.599976	8.4240
QPSK 2/3	2	0.67	2 - 4.5	0.2	48.239976	9.6480	28.943976	5.7888
16 QAM 1/4	4	0.5	4.5 - 6	0.17	71.999976	12.2400	43.199976	7.3440
16 QAM 2/3	4	0.67	6 - 8.5	0.16	96.479976	15.4368	57.887976	9.2621
16 QAM 4/5	4	0.8	8.5 - 10.8	0.09	115.19998	10.3680	69.119976	6.2208
64 QAM 1/2	6	0.5	10.8 - 12.5	0.08	107.99998	8.6400	64.799976	5.1840
64 QAM 2/3	6	0.67	12.5 - 13.5	0.07	144.71998	10.1304	86.831976	6.0782
Cell Average Throughput (MAC) = $\sum Pa \times Ra$					87.1992	22.3195		
Capacity per site					261.5975	156.9585		

(c) 1800 MHz-850 MHz

The capacity of site throughput for the frequency of 1800 MHz downlink direction of 101.0879 Mbps and uplink direction of 60.6527 Mbps. Downlink site throughput capacity of 73.5407 Mbps and uplink direction 88.2489 Mbps. Then, downlink site throughput capacity of 261.5975 Mbps and uplink direction of 156.9585 Mbps.

(7) Site Number Calculation

TABLE 7 NUMBER OF SITE BASED ON CAPACITY

Item	LTE		LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation)	
	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink	Downlink
Coverage Area (km ²)	331.76		331.76	
User	35711		16070	
SUT (Kbps)	23.4535	245.4331	23.4535	245.4331
Network Throughput (Mbps)	854.2918	8939.8816	384.43	4022.96
Cell Average Throughput (Mbps)	20.2176	33.696	52.3195	87.1992
Site Capacity (Mbps)	60.6528	101.088	156.9585	261.5976
Number of Site	14	88	2	15
Cell Coverage (km ²)	23.55421507	3.751386907	135.45304	21.57307952
Cell Radius (km ²)	3.475497756	1.387006906	8.33445243	3.326126531

The number of sites for LTE (FDD) is 88 sites, while for LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) are 15 sites. The number of sites used for the simulation is taken at the most number of sites it is based on to get good coverage.

E. Expansion Planning Based on Coverage

(1) Maximum Allowable Pathloss (MAPL)

Maximum Allowable Pathloss (MAPL) is the maximum allowable loss value. MAPL is calculated on the uplink and downlink side, so when the customer loses less than the MAPL value that has been calculated then the customer still can access the service.

TABLE 8. MAXIMUM ALLOWABLE PATHLOSS (MAPL)[8]

Link budget for MAPL & Cell radius calculation					
Morphology	Sub Urban		Sub Urban		Formula
	UL	DL	UL	DL	
Duplex mode	FDD				
Carrier frequency (MHz)	1800 ; 850				
MIMO scheme	UL = 2x2 ; DL = 4x4				
Transmitter	UE	eNodeB	UE	eNodeB	
Max total Tx power (dBm)	23	43	23	46	A
RB to distributed power	3	100	3	100	C
Subcarriers to distributed power	36	1200	36	1200	D = 12*C
Subcarrier power (dBm)	7.437	12.208	7.437	12.208	E = A - 10*log(D)
Tx antenna gain (dBi)	0	17	0	17	G
Tx cable loss (dB)	0	0.5	0	0.5	H
EIRP per subcarrier (dBm)	7.437	28.708	7.437	28.708	J = E+G-H
Receiver	eNodeB	UE	eNodeB	UE	
SINR (dB)	-6	-5	-6	-5	K
Rx noise figure (dB)	2	3	2	3	L
Receiver sensitivity (dBm)	136.239	134.239	136.239	134.239	M = K-L-174+10*log(15000)
Rx antenna gain (dBi)	17	0	17	0	N
Rx body loss (dB)	2	2	2	2	P
Interference margin	2	3.13	2	3.13	Q
Min signal reception strength (dBm)	132.239	129.109	132.239	129.109	R = M+P+Q
Pathloss & Shadow fading margin					
Penetration loss (dB)	10	10	11	11	S
Shadow fading margin (dB)	4	4	5	5	T
Max allowed path loss (dB)	142.676	143.817	132.676	133.817	U = J+N-R-S-T

The MAPL value of 142.676 dB for the frequency of 1800 MHz, and 132.676 dB for the frequency of 850 MHz.

(2) Calculation of Radius Cell

After getting the MAPL value, next is to determine the radius cell.

TABLE 9 RADIUS CELL

Propagation model	Cost231-hata		Okumurra Hata		
eNodeB antenna height (m)	30	30	30	30	V
UE antenna height (m)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	W
Frequency (Mhz)	1800	1800	850	850	X
a(Hr)	0.04297	0.04297	0.01365	0.01365	
Cell radius (km)	1.5281132	1.6464646	1.571968	1.693716323	

(3) Number of Site Calculation

After obtaining cell radius value for each frequency then next determine the amount of site for planning expansion of LTE network to be done.

TABLE 10 NUMBER OF SITE BASED ON COVERAGE

District	Large District (km ²)	LTE (FDD)		LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation)	
		Cell Coverage (km ²)	Total Site	Cell Coverage (km ²)	Total Site
Leles	73.51	4.55	16	4.82	15
Bayongbong	47.63	4.55	10	4.82	10
Cisurupan	80.88	4.55	18	4.82	17
Tarogong Kidul	19.46	4.55	4	4.82	4
Tarogong Kaler	50.57	4.55	11	4.82	10
Samarang	59.71	4.55	13	4.82	12
Jumlah	331.76		73		69

The total site obtained based on the coverage calculation for LTE FDD is 73 sites, while for LTE-A of 69 sites.

F. Trade Off

Based on the calculation of expansion planning based on the capacity and coverage that has been done obtained.

MAPL Capacity= 141.2016467 dB MAPL Coverage = 142.6837993 dB

For the allowed trade off is 0-5 dB range because the difference between MAPL capacity and MAPL coverage has been calculated <5 dB then the calculation of the number of sites that have been done can be used. The number of sites used for the simulation is taken the most number of sites, this is because to get good signal quality. So for LTE (FDD) of 88 sites and LTE-A 69 site.

IV. RESULT SIMULATION AND DISCUSSION

A. Simulation of Initial Conditions

The extension areas consist of 6 sub-districts: Leles sub- district (1), Tarogong Kaler sub-district (2), Samarang sub- district (3), Bayongbong sub-district (4), Cisurupan sub- district (5), and Tarogong Kidul sub-district (6).

(a) RSRP (b) SINR (c) CDF RSRP (d) CDF SINR
Figure 3. Initial Condition of LTE RSRP and SINR Parameters

Based on Fig.3 above shows that in the area there are blank spots in some districts are marked with numbers 1,2,3,4,5, and 6. RSRP value average -90.37 dBm and the average SINR value 10.88 dB. Then the percentage of RSRP > -100 dBm is 75.067% and the percentage of SINR > -5 dB is 73.416%. This value does not meet the KPI standards for operators.

(a) Throughput (b) User Connected
Figure 4 Initial Condition of LTE Throughput & User Connected

Based on Fig. 4 the simulation results throughput of network conditions on the initial conditions average throughput per user of 17.580 Mbps and the percentage of users who failed to connect is 92.8%, while the percentage of users who successfully connected (user connected) is 7.2%.

B. Simulation After Expansion

(1) LTE (FDD) Simulation

Based on the results of the previous calculation of the number of sites in the planning coverage area obtained 88 sites for LTE (FDD).

Figure 5. Expansion Simulation Results LTE (FDD) RSRP and SINR Parameters

Fig. 5 Expansion Simulation Results LTE (FDD) RSRP and SINR Parameters Fig. 5 shows that there has been an expansion of coverage area in some districts in the area. RSRP average after expansion is -65,91 dBm. While the signal quality or SINR average after the expansion is 18.02 dB. Then the percentage of RSRP > -100 dBm is 95.1% and the percentage of SINR > 5 dB is 96.4%. This value meets KPI standards for operators.

Figure 6. Expansion Simulation Results LTE (FDD) Throughput and User Connected Parameters

Fig. 6 shows that the LTE throughput simulation results (FDD) obtained average per-user throughput of 24.962 Mbps and the percentage of throughput > 12 Mbps is 89.7%. This value meets the KPI operator standard. Then for the percentage of users who failed to connect is 6.7%, while the percentage of successful users connected is 93.3%.

(2) Simulation of LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR

Based on the previous calculation, the number of sites in the planning of coverage coverage area for LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR obtained 69 sites.

Figure 7. Results of simulation expansion of LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR RSRP and SINR parameters

Fig. 7 shows the average RSRP after expansion of LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR -48,88 dBm and SNR 22.5 dB. Then the percentage of RSRP > -100 dBm is 98.4% and the percentage of SINR > 5 dB is 96.59%. This value meets KPI standards for operators.

(a) Throughput (b) User Connected

Figure 8. Results of simulation expansion of LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR Throughput and User Connected parameters

Fig.8 shows an average throughput per user of 28.923 Mbps. The value is larger and there has been an increase compared to the LTE (FDD) simulation results. This value also meets the standards of KPI. Then the percentage of users who failed to connect is 5.5%, while the percentage of successful users connected is 94.5%.

C. Analysis of Simulation Results

Based on the results of simulations that have been done following table xi shows the final result of LTE coverage area coverage in Garut district.

TABLE XI End RESULT OF LTE COVERAGE EXPANSION SIMULATION

No.	Parameter	Initial Condition	LTE (FDD)	LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) And SFR
1	RSRP (dBm)	-90.37	- 65.91	-48.88
2	SINR (dB)	10.88	18.02	22.5
3	Throughput (Mbps)	17.580	24.962	28.923
4	User Connected (%)	7.2 %	93.3%	94.5%
5	Total Site (site)	15	88	69
6	Wide Area (km ²)	27.71	331.76	331.76
7	Percentage (%)	7.70857	92.291429	92.291429

Based on the simulation result of coverage area that has been done, as recommendation for operator, better to be implemented in Garut area is expanding coverage area using LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR. This is due to the consideration of cost efficiency for the number of sites built fewer than 69 sites, as well as better network performance in terms of coverage with RSRP average -48.88 dBm, and better network quality with average SINR 22 , 5 dB, 28.923 Mbps throughput, and user connected 94.5%. The expansion of coverage area in Garut area using LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR become effective solution in utilizing 5 MHz bandwidth in band 5 (850 MHz), and 10 MHz bandwidth in band 3 (1800 MHz), so that it can improve the frequency spectrum limited.

IV. CONCLUSION

- 1) The number of sites needed for LTE coverage area expansion in Garut district area is 88 sites for expansion using LTE (FDD) and 69 sites for expansion using LTE- A (Carrier Aggregation) combined with SFR.

- 2) Simulation result of coverage area expansion in Garut area using LTE (FDD), got average RSRP parameter value -
- 3) 65.91 dBm, SINR average 18.02 dB, throughput 24,962 Mbps, and user connected 93.3%. While the simulation result of coverage area expansion in Garut area using LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) combined with SFR, got the average RSRP parameter value -48.88 dBm, SINR average 22.5 dB, throughput 28.923 Mbps, and user connected 94.5%. The values of those parameters have met the KPI operator standard.
- 4) Simulation result of coverage area expansion in Garut area, obtained coverage area increase of 331,76 km² (92.291429%) using LTE (FDD) and LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) combined with SFR compared with initial condition equal to 27.71 km² (7.70857%).
- 5) Use of carrier aggregation feature on band 3 (1800 MHz) with 10 MHz and band 5 (850 MHz) bandwidth with 5MHz bandwidth to improve RSRP, SINR, throughput and user connected values. While the use of SFR features, both to minimize interference in cell centers and in the cell edge so that the quality of the network is maintained.
- 6) Better expansion of LTE coverage to be implemented in Garut area is the expansion of coverage area using LTE-A (Carrier Aggregation) and SFR. This is due to consideration of cost savings for the number of sites built less and better network performance.

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